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Water, Wastewater Treatment and Reuse / *Prerada vode, pročišćavanje i recikliranje otpadnih voda*
Oral presentation / *Usmeno priopćenje*

Strategic planning of wastewater treatment pathways contributing its reuse

Djurdja KERKEZ, Milena BEČELIĆ-TOMIN, Vesna PEŠIĆ, Dejan KRČMAR, Dragana TOMAŠEVIĆ PILIPOVIĆ, Anita LEOVAC MAĆERAK, Aleksandra KULIĆ MANDIĆ

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Abstract

The Green Agenda for the Western Balkans, through its pillars, addresses the initiatives to support the region in developing circular economy (CE) strategies and fighting pollution of air, water and soil. According to this wastewater can potentially contribute to the nexus of water, energy and material recovery, with regard to the circular-economy design. Many challenges but also opportunities rise when considering reclamation and reuse of wastewater to increase water resources, with special attention paying particular attention to the risks for human health, recovery of nutrients, or highly added-value products (e.g., metals and biomolecules, etc.), valorization of sewage sludge, and/or recovery of energy. This adds new light onto wastewater treatment technologies and choosing the best pathway for resource recovery. A structured approach, based on multicriteria analysis is needed for selecting technologies for resource recovery from wastewater. Integrated resource recovery schemes focus on the best-performing resources for a given scenario, additional resources that can be captured, and potential process enhancements. To decide the final strategy, treatment methods using the original mass balance model are compared. This sort of strategic planning tool is necessary to accelerate the water sector's CE transition.

Keywords: wastewater management, circular economy, wastewater treatment and reuse

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